

Synthesis of N¹-Isonicotinyl-3,5-Dimethyl-4-(Substituted Azo)-1 : 2-Diazole

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Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) and their derivatives are generally used as anti-tubercular and antitumor agent. We synthesised the substituted azo-2,4-pentanedione at reactive methylene position. The substituted azo-2,4-pentanedione (Z) in glacial acetic acid and INH were heated to form N¹-isonicotinyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(Z)-1 : 2-diazole and their derivatives. Their R_f values, chemical analyses and IR, NMR spectra were recorded which helps in establishing the structures and mechanism of the reactions.

DURING the last thirty years diazole ring has attracted much attention as they have been the basis of numerous dyes, drugs and number of diazoles anaesthetics have been reported¹. Some diazoles synthesised by condensation of β-ketones with substituted hydrazones²⁻⁴ shows antibacterial activity⁵. Sulphadruugs are well known chemotherapeutic agent isonicotinic acid⁶, isonicotinic acid hydrazide⁷ (INH) and their derivatives are generally used as antitubercular⁸ and antitumor⁹ agent. Recently Saharia¹⁰ *et al.* synthesised substituted, aryl azo diazoles from different substituted hydrazines and studied their activity.

Practically no work has been done in which sulphadruugs, substituted aromatic amines are condensed at reactive methylene position of β-diketones to forms sulphasubstituted phenyl-azo-2, 4-pentanedione which further forms N¹-isonicotinyl-4-(substituted azo)-1 : 2-diazole by the cyclisation of INH from synthesised pentanedione. It has therefore been considered worthwhile to synthesise 1-isonicotinyl-3-methyl/phenyl-4-N-substituted-*p*-sulphonyl/benzene azo diazole and to study their antitumor activity.

The probable mechanism of the reaction is as given below :

Where

Experimental

All the chemicals used are either BDH or E. Merck quality except INH (C.C.P, Najibabad).

Synthesis of substituted azo-2, 4-pentanedione :

Aromatic amine (0.025 mole) was converted into diazonium chloride and then was run into a well cooled, stirred mixture of sodium-acetate (15 g) and 2, 4-pentanedione (0.025 mole) in ethanol (60 ml) and shaken vigorously. A coloured precipitate separated which was recrystallised from ethanol. By adopting similar procedure, a few substituted azo-2, 4-pentanedione have been synthesised and their characteristics are recorded in Table 1.

Synthesis of Isonicotinyl Hydrazone (Y) azo-2, 4-pentanedione :

INH(0.05 mole) dissolved in about 3 c.c. of ethanol and substituted azo (0.05 mole) compound in 3 c.c. of dimethyl formamide (DMF) was heated for 10 minutes. On cooling, a coloured crystalline hydrazone separated out. Filtered, washed with little ethanol and recrystallised from ethyl alcohol/DMF mixture. By adopting similar procedure, a few substituted hydrazone have been synthesised and their characteristics are recorded in Table 2.

Synthesis of N¹-Isonicotinyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(Z)-1 : 2-diazole :

Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (0.07 mole) and substituted azo-2, 4-pentanedione (0.07 mole) were dissolved in sufficient quantity of glacial acetic acid and contents refluxed on a water bath for 2 hours. On cooling, a solid coloured compound separated out.

Filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol/DMF mixture. By adopting a similar procedure a few substituted 1 : 2 diazoles have been synthesised and their characteristics are recorded in Table 3.

The substituted azo-2, 4-pentanedione isonicotinyl hydrazone (Y)-azo-2, 4-pentanedione and N¹-isonicotinyl-3, 5-dimethyl-4-(Z)-1 : 2-diazole formed were subjected to thin layer chromatography. In each case only one spot was observed showing the formation of single product. The formation of isonicotinyl hydrazone out of two ketonic group¹¹ only one ketonic group react for the formation of hydrazone another ketonic group remain as an enolic form^{12,13}.

Infra-Red Spectra :

IR spectra were run in KBr and Nujol. The spectra had characteristic peaks λ_{Max} 930 cm⁻¹ (s) and 820 cm⁻¹ (aromatic ring), 1575 cm⁻¹ (-N=N-), 1620 cm⁻¹ (>C=N-), 1745 (>C=O),

1725 cm⁻¹ (Heterocyclic five membered diazole ring) and 1480 cm⁻¹ (six membered heterocyclic pyridine ring)¹⁴ were recorded which helps in establishing the structures and mechanism of the reactions.

NMR Spectra :

The structure of hydrazones and diazoles were also confirmed by NMR spectra studies.

Hydrazone :

NMR(CDCl₃): δ 2.54(d, J=9 Hz, 3H, -CoCH₃), 1.08(s, 3H, -CH₃), 7.15-7.75(m, 8H, aromatic), 8.13-8.24(s, 1H, -NH).

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTIC OF SUBSTITUTED AZO-2,4-PENTANEDIONE. (X)-AZO-2,4-PENTANEDIONE.

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{X}-\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{CH}-\text{C}-\text{CH}_3 \\ | \quad \quad \quad || \\ \text{COCH}_3 \quad \quad \text{O} \end{array}$$

Sl. No.	X	M.P.°C	Molecular formula	Colour	Rf. value
1.	Phenyl	70	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂	PY	0.7784
2.	2-Chlorophenyl	120	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	DY	0.9448
3.	3-Chlorophenyl	95	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	LY	0.6779
4.	4-Chlorophenyl	127	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	SPY	0.8139
5.	2-Nitrophenyl	174	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂	OY	0.9454
6.	3-Nitrophenyl	125	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂	GY	0.7518
7.	4-Nitrophenyl	215 d	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂	DY	0.7305
8.	2-Methylphenyl	102	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	GY	0.6763
9.	4-Methylphenyl	89	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	SPYN	0.8484
10.	4-Methoxyphenyl	95	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂	SPY	0.9526
11.	3-Nitro, 4-methylphenyl	165	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂	LY	0.9369
12.	4-Bromophenyl	137	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br	SPYN	0.7735
13.	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	90	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₃	LY	0.6852
14.	N-Aceto-4-aminophenyl	218	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂	OY	0.9202
15.	4-Aminodiphenyl	250 d	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂	BR	0.9585
16.	1-Naphthyl	115	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂	R	0.6842
17.	2-Naphthyl	125	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂	DY	0.6763
18.	2-Sulphanilamidobenzene	212	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂ S	GY	0.7449
19.	N ¹ -2-Pyridyl sulphanilamidobenzene	210	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	OY	0.7394
20.	N ¹ -2-Thiazolyl sulphanilamidobenzene	190	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	PY	0.7404
21.	N ¹ -2-Pyrimidyl sulphanilamidobenzene	185	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂ S	BY	0.7811
22.	N ¹ -2-Guanyl sulphanilamidobenzene	250 d	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₆ S	PY	0.7141
23.	N ¹ -2-Acetyl sulphanilamidobenzene	130	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₂ S	LY	0.2869
24.	N ¹ -2(4,6-dimethyl) Pyrimidyl-sulphanilamido benzene	185	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	PY	0.6237
25.	N ¹ -2-Quinoxalyl sulphanilamidobenzene	144	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ S	RW	0.3065
26.	2,3-Dimethyl-1-phenyl pyrazolone	180	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂	O	0.9205

Note :

- I. Elemental analyses of the compounds were found satisfactory.
- II. Yield of the compounds ranges between 60 to 80%.
- III. P= Pale, Y=Yellow, D=Dark, S=Shining, G=Golden, B=Brown, O=Orange, W=White, L=Light, N=Needles and R=Red.

(Table 3 Contd.)

Sl. No.	Z	M.P.°C	Molecular formula	Colour	Rf. Value
10.	4-Methoxyphenylazo	145	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂	SPYN	0.9443
11.	3-Nitro, 4-methylphenylazo	147	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	PY	0.9376
12.	4-Bromophenylazo	115	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Br	SPY	0.8880
13.	2,4,6-Tribromophenylazo	108	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Br ₃	OY	0.9397
14.	N-Aceto-4-aminophenylazo	225	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂	DY	0.9533
15.	4-Aminodiphenylazo	235	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ON ₂	OY	0.8720
16.	1-Naphthylazo	190	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂	DB	0.9604
17.	2-Naphthylazo	195	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂	PYF	0.9656
18.	2-Sulphanilamidobenzeneazo	185	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	GPYF	0.9412
19.	N ¹ -2-Pyridyl sulphanilamidobenzeneazo	199	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	DY	0.8828
20.	N ¹ -2-Thiazolyl sulphanilamidobenzeneazo	230 d	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	OR	0.6246
21.	N ¹ -2-Pyrimidyl sulphanilamidobenzeneazo	205	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	EOF	0.4113
22.	N ¹ -2-Guanyl sulphanilamidobenzeneazo	238 d	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	PY	0.7765
23.	N ¹ -2-Acetyl sulphanilamidobenzeneazo	232	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	OY	0.2441
24.	N ¹ -2-(4,6-Dimethyl)-pyrimidyl sulphanilamido benzene azo	190	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	RY	0.2878
25.	N ¹ -2-Quinoxalyl sulphanilamido benzene azo	175	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	GY	0.9306
26.	2,3-Dimethyl-1-phenyl pyrazolone azo	176	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	SON	0.8898

Note : I. Elemental analyses of the compounds were found satisfactory.
 II. Yield of the compounds ranges between 65 to 90%.
 III. L=Light, Y=Yellow, S=Shining, P=Pale, R=Red, B=Brown, G=Golden, F=Flakes, N=Needles, O=Orange and D=Dity.

Diazole :

NMR(CDCl₃) δ2.52(s, 3H, CH₃), 2.65(s, 3H, CH₃), 7.1-7.8(m, -10H, aromatic).

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